

**TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF LANGUAGE SKILLS
IN ENGLISH CLASSES**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7275892>

Abstract: This article examines the problems of improving the effectiveness of English language classes, with special attention to the development of each of the foreign language skills, listening comprehension, speaking, reading and writing.

Keywords: language skills, listening comprehension, speaking, reading, writing, active and passive language skills, facilitator, extensive reading.

Language is the primary means of communication and communication between people around the world and for establishing good relations between countries. It is no secret that in the modern world, English language stands out from other languages as a language used by more people living in different states, countries and regions. Today, it has become a leading language in many fields such as medicine, engineering, journalism, education, business, science, technology and mass media, pharmacology and scientific research. There are several factors that have brought English to the status of an international language. Due to the fact that most of the information on the Internet is in English, the demand for specialists who know this language and have the opportunity to get the necessary information from the websites in a timely manner is increasing day by day.

Taking into account the above points, we can say that one of the urgent issues of today is that Uzbek youth who are learning English as a foreign language should master this language thoroughly and become experts who can use it correctly. Taking this need into account, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoev's address to the Oliy Majlis states, among other things: "Our great thinker poet Mir Alisher Navoi addressed the youth in his time and wrote: "If you want sunshine, perfect your profession." Indeed, a person who wants to radiate joyous light like the sun to people, to do good, should strive for perfection and master various sciences and professions.

We would not be mistaken if we say that it is impossible to achieve such goals as our great grandfather said in the present era without learning foreign languages

perfectly. Following this urgent demand, I suggest to prioritize the study of physics and foreign languages in the coming year."

In the modern world, where there is a great demand for the English language and for professionals who master it well, comprehensive learning of it requires careful formation of all skills. In order to master English at or near the level of native speakers, teachers will have to organize exercises, assignments and lessons aimed at mastering all language skills in the educational process and play the role of a facilitator (assistant) rather than a traditional teacher in the language learning process. These language skills are: listening, speaking, reading, writing. Each of these skills is important to achieving the desired goal of language learning. Therefore, their mastery and development remains one of the necessary tasks of today. Listening comprehension and reading are considered passive (receptive) skills, because they do not create language material, but rather, they help to receive material created by others. Speaking and writing are active (creative) skills, because students express their thoughts in the form of oral or written sentences with the help of language material. Thus, active and passive skills are not displayed at the same time. Listening before speaking, reading before writing (or vice versa).

If the language learner does not fully master each one and make proper use of their potential, he or she may not be able to achieve the desired goal. At the same time, students should consider them equally important, because each of them is a separate, independent phenomenon related to language learning. In addition, teachers should use modern and advanced pedagogical technologies, methods and approaches in their lessons.

Listening comprehension is the first of the four skills to develop. All skills are important, but listening comprehension is the most important. This is because it is the key to successful communication. Listening comprehension is a skill that develops faster than speaking, and it often affects reading and writing skills as well. Without well-developed and effective listening comprehension skills, language learners may not fully understand the message being conveyed and communication may not be successful.

According to Vandergrift, listening is a complex and active process in which the listener tries to compare the message he hears with his prior knowledge. According to Hadfield, listening comprehension is the most difficult skill in learning a foreign language. It is no secret that many teachers do not pay enough attention to the development of listening comprehension skills. It should be said that when traditional lessons were given, this issue was not given any

importance at all. Later, when non-traditional pedtechnologies began to develop, a slight shift in this regard was noticed. In this regard, Flowers and Miller say, "When tasks are given in the medium of the language being studied, language learners become immersed in that language." Listening comprehension, in particular, remained one of the most important tools of the direct method, but it was not treated as a separate skill to be mastered, inductive learning by language learners hearing the same material over and over again. were busy with, and teachers did not introduce active listening comprehension tasks into the lesson process. Similar situations were observed in other audiolingual and grammatical methods of language teaching.

Later, the acquisition of listening comprehension increased to the level of language learners learning by interacting in real-life situations. In the era of today's highly developed information media, it would be appropriate to use authentic materials widely in the formation of listening comprehension skills and development of skills in English.

The advantages of tasks aimed at teaching listening comprehension include:

- ❖ successful listening comprehension ensures full understanding of the language (situation);
- ❖ serves to speak fluently and fluently;
- ❖ helps students to correctly assess the speech situation;
- ❖ forms the ability of students to adequately respond to the opinions expressed by the interlocutor;
- ❖ helps to fully understand the content;
- ❖ useful in mastering new concepts and content presented in new material;
- ❖ helps to strengthen existing knowledge and skills;
- ❖ helps to gain the interlocutor's trust and respect.

In the lesson, the teacher can use many exercises and tasks aimed at developing students' listening comprehension skills. Listening and listening to various presentations, exhibitions, shows, TV shows, and radio broadcasts presented in English outside of the classroom will lead to a sharp improvement in listening comprehension skills.

Speaking is an active skill and students need a lot of practice to develop it. Speaking is the most difficult skill to master when learning a foreign language, because you have to respond to the question asked during the conversation. Effective communication in a real conversation is only possible by practicing speaking a lot. Speaking is a skill that tests a language learner's knowledge in real-life situations. Even today, we can see that many teachers are engaged in

repeating and reinforcing speech patterns and memorizing various texts and dialogues.

There are two types of reading: extensive and intensive reading. Extensive reading occurs when a person reads for pleasure. This type of reading is convenient for language learners to choose and study according to their own preferences. Through extensive reading, language learners can improve their reading skills. Because this method is an effective way to develop language learners' vocabulary and grammatical competence, it is appropriate for teachers to engage their students in as much reading as possible.

Intensive reading means reading a specific text and doing new words or grammar exercises and tasks based on that text. In this, students analyze the text and pay attention to the use of language materials. In intensive reading, some students try to grasp the idea presented by the main topic and cannot move on from it. Some of them pay attention to the meaning and usage of each word and sentence and read with greater interest. Nevertheless, the teacher should choose the text, taking into account the interests of both types of students, and create interesting exercises and tasks for the children.

In conclusion, it can be said that as the position and prestige of the English language in the world community is increasing, it should be learned in our country as well. It is important to fully master each of the four skills that occupy the main place in learning the English language. These skills are listening, speaking, reading and writing (TLS), and effective language acquisition requires the development of all of them. Systematic design and planning of the process of teaching foreign languages through the development of language skills requires the training of foreign language teachers with the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications..

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